

WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

Agroforestry in CAP Strategic Plans

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Authors (eds)	Gerry Lawson (EURAF)
Contact	policy@euraf.net
Approved	Marie Gosme (INRAE)
Contributors	Annex A - , Daphne Ruigrok, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Belgium
	Annex B - Bohdan Lojka, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Czech Republic, Jakub Houska, Výzkumný Ústav Silva Taroucy Pro Krajinu a Okrasné Zahradnictví (VUKOZ), Czech Republic
	Annex C - Julie Rohde Birk, Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug P/S (IOL), Denmark
	Annex D - Michael de Herder, European Forest Institute (EFI), Joensuu, Finland
	Annex E - Fabien Liagre, AGROOF Société Coopérative et Participative (AGROOF), France

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WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

	Annex F Rico Hübner, Deutscher Fachverband für Agroforstwirtschaft (DeFAF) e.V., Germany
	Annex G Vasilios Papanastasis, Hellenic Agroforestry Network ELLINIKO AGRODASIKO DIKTYO EAD (HAN), Greece
	Annex H Zita Szalai Magdolna, Hungarian Permaculture Association (MAPA), Hungary
	Annex I Margharita Tranchina, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSSA), Pisa, Italy
	Annex J Dagnija Lazdina, Latvian Forest Owners Association (LFOA), Latvia
	Annex K Evert Prins, Stichting Louis Bolk Instituut (LBI), The Netherlands
	Annex L Ana Tomás, Moinhos de Vento -Agroecology Research Centre (MVARC), Portugal
	Annex M Katja Bajec, Sinergise Laboratorij za Geografske Informacijske Sisteme (Sinergise)
	Annex N Manuel Bertomeu, University of Extremadura (UEX), Spain

Contents Version 1.2

Summary	3
1 Introduction	5
2 CAP Strategic Plan Legislation	5
2.1 CAP Strategic Plan Regulation (2021/2115)	6
2.2 CAP Horizontal Regulation (2021/2116)	7
2.3 Delegated and Implementing Acts relating to the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation	8
3 Policy Overview of 14 Member States	9
3.1 Agroforestry Definitions	9
3.2 Landscape Features (Pillar I)	10
3.3 Permanent Grassland Definitions (Pillar I)	11
3.4 Eco-schemes (Pillar I - Article 31)	16
3.5 Rural Development (Pillar II)	16
3.6 The EU “CAP Simplification Regulation”	18
3.7 The Nature Restoration Regulation	18
3.8 The LULUCF Regulation and National Energy and Climate Plans	19
3.9 Agroforestry in the EU Framework Regulation for Carbon Removals (CRCF)	20
3.10 Conclusions and future work.	21
ANNEXES	23
A Belgium - Flanders	23

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WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

B Czechia	23
C Denmark	23
D Finland	23
E France	23
F Germany	23
G Greece	23
H Hungary	23
I Italy	23
J Latvia	23
K Netherlands	24
L Portugal	24
M Slovenia	24
N Spain	24
References	25

Summary

This report summarises agroforestry related policies in the CAP Strategic plans of the 14 countries involved in the DigitAF Project.

1. **Definitions of agroforestry** are very variable, with upper thresholds of trees/ha set between 50 and 300 trees per hectare. Few minimum density thresholds are applied. Only BE-FL points out that tree densities can be higher than the threshold in young plantations as long as agricultural production is maintained and trees are thinned as they become too large. How Member States (MS) apply these thresholds will only be apparent when the LPIS systems and basic payment eligibility quotients are examined.
2. **Landscape Features** (Pillar I) are important in all MS definitions of GAEC-8, and are also key to the Biodiversity Strategy (and Nature Restoration Law) aim of 10% "space for nature". MS have considerably increased their inclusion of tree-landscape-features compared to the previous CAP, with greater implementation of hedges (20 MS), trees in line (21 MS), and isolated trees (19 MS). There is a need for conformity between the maximum block size of tree groups (copses/groves) and the minimum size of forest recognised in national legislation and Annex II of the LULUCF Regulation. MS should use LPIS data to observe compliance with GAEC-8 and other "space for nature" indicators (e.g. I.21, R.34). Indicators at a coarser scale (like LUCAS) will not provide a link between specific Measures and farmers activities. Landscape features are automatically eligible for Basic Payments and can be viewed as "permanent" to comply with rules for the certification of carbon farming.
3. **Definitions of Permanent Grassland** have become more inclusive since the Omnibus Regulation in 2017. Nine MS have adopted wording which includes "trees and/or shrubs provided that grasses and other herbaceous species remain predominant". A further 9 countries have adopted a definition where land with shrubs and/or trees producing animal feed can be classed as permanent grassland, even when herbaceous forage is absent in these areas. Three MS have used this classification over their entire agricultural area.

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WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

4. **Ecoschemes (Pillar I).** Schemes specifically mentioning agroforestry have been implemented only in DE and EL, and the budgets proposed mean that the schemes will have little impact. Other Ecoschemes in a majority of MS *could* be interpreted to support agroforestry but there is, so far, no indication of this interpretation from these countries.
5. **Rural Development Measures (Pillar II).** Measures to assist agroforestry exist only in BE-FL, CZ, ES, FR, IT and PT. In IT and ES they will be implemented only in 4-5 regions. However other Rural Development options (ENVCLIM for annual payments and INVEST for single payments) could be relevant to agroforestry if so interpreted by MS. These interpretations will be important in regions of ES and IT which have not implemented the main agroforestry measure, and in other countries which have, so far, chosen not to implement agroforestry at all. This can be clarified in future CSP updates.
6. **Carbon Farming and LULUCF Sequestration.** Carbon Farming options in CAP Strategic Plans will be reviewed in DigitAF Task 1.3. The revised LULUCF regulation became law on 11.5.2024 and has presented MS with the need to ensure that their Strategic Plans and other measures related to land use, will deliver their country's share of the new target of -310 MtCO₂ by 2030 (and intermediate targets for 2025 onwards - as specified in National Energy and Climate Plans). However, very few MS have evaluated the impact of any of their CAP Measures in terms of tonnes of CO₂e, and the existing CAP Result Indicators are inadequate for the task¹. Member States need an emergency programme of afforestation, agroforestation and settlement-tree-planting. EURAF [Policy Briefing #26](#) proposes 250,000 ha/ year in the period 2025 to 2050.
7. **Other EU Regulations and disincentives to agroforestry.** Agroforestry is impacted by a range of environmental, agricultural and climate legislation at the EU and national level. The DigitAF Project has summarised relevant EU policies in 10 Briefings, produced over the past 12 months, available on the [EURAF website](#).

¹ **Impact indicators** (European Commission 2023) are due to be produced by MS, but they are aggregated at a national scale and have little relevance to farmers. DigitAF Task 1.2 will evaluate options to produce biophysical Impact indicators I.10 to I.22 from remotely sensed information and IACS/LPIS data at the farm-scale..

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1 Introduction

Version 1 of his report was delivered in Month 12 of the DigitAF Project (June 2023), with summaries of CAP policies in the 14 Member States associated with DigitAF.

Version 2 has been revised to replace individual country sections with links to Policy Briefings which are being updated in the case of 13 countries and have been completed in the case of Spain. The following reviewer comments have also been addressed:

- add a more detailed introduction and/or conclusion section in which the objective of the report would be specified, including how the results of this report will be taken up in the further work of the project;
- describe how the report was compiled, which data sources have been used etc.
- strengthen the comparative analysis of cross-country variations.
- add a discussion to give a more critical analysis of the implications of the findings for policy development.

The agroforestry-related policies summarised here are primarily based on an analysis of the initial versions of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans of Member States (MS). These Strategic Plans, and detailed national rules and guidelines are being continuously amended and are being summarised in Policy Briefings for the 14 countries represented in DigitAF: [BE-E](#), [CZ](#), [DK](#), [FI](#), [FR](#), [DE](#), [EL](#), [HU](#), [IT](#), [LV](#), [NL](#), [PT](#), [SL](#), [ES](#).

Additional sections have been added in Version 2 on: the EU CAP Simplification Regulation, the Nature Restoration Regulation, the revised LULUCF Regulation, the National Energy and Climate Plans and the EU Carbon Removals Framework Regulation.

2 CAP Strategic Plan Legislation

There are nine objectives in the new CAP 2023-2028, as legislated in the CAP Sustainable Plan Regulation (2021/2115). Three of these are related to environment, climate change, natural resources and ecosystems, and have most relevance to agroforestry:

- **Objective 4:** *Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy* ([brief](#))
- **Objective 5:** *Foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air* ([brief](#))
- **Objective 6:** *Contribution to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes* ([brief](#))

Member States were asked to include a SWOT analysis in their CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs) of the fit between proposed measures and these Objectives. A small number of countries mentioned agroforestry specifically in these SWOT analyses. This reflected the Commission's analysis of preliminary documents and their "Recommendations to Member States on their CAP Strategic Plans" revealed that agroforestry or silvopastoralism was mentioned in only 11 of the 27 recommendation letters, despite being stressed in the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020b), the Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020a) and the European Green Deal (Worms and Lawson, 2020). See EURAF [Policy Briefing #10](#) (Lawson, 2021)

On the 6th December 2021 the three Regulations defining the new CAP were signed into law. Two of these specifically mention **agroforestry**.

2.1 CAP Strategic Plan Regulation (2021/2115)

Regulation 2021/2115 mentions agroforestry in **nine sections** (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #14](#)):

- **Recital 14** ... asks MS are asked to ensure that their framework definition of ‘agricultural area’ includes “**agroforestry systems**”,
- **Recital 26** ... includes **agroforestry** in a list of high-quality sustainable farming practices
- **Recital 72** ... includes “**establishment of agroforestry systems**” in a list of environmentally-friendly production systems which management commitments should support with payments covering additional costs and income foregone ... and that these payments can go beyond seven-years when duly justified.
- **Recital 73** ... notes that forestry interventions should contribute to the New EU Forestry Strategy for 2030, and should include **widening the use of agroforestry systems**, including special mention of agroforestry in the context of “effective carbon storage and sequestration”.
- **Article 4 Para 3** ... confirms that ‘Agricultural area’ shall be determined in such a way as to comprise arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland, including when they form **agroforestry systems** on that area”.²
- **Article 15 Para 3** ... stresses that farm advisory services, shall offer appropriate assistance along the cycle of the farm development, including for the setting-up for the first time, conversion of production patterns towards consumer demand, innovative practises, agricultural techniques for resilience to climate change, including **agroforestry** and agroecology, improved animal welfare, and where necessary safety standards and social support.
- **Article 70 Para 2a** ... confirms that Member States shall provide payments only for commitments which: (b) go beyond the relevant minimum requirements for the use of fertiliser and plant protection products or for animal welfare, as well as other relevant mandatory requirements established by national and Union law; that this requirement does not apply to commitments related to **agroforestry systems** and the maintenance of afforested areas;
- **Result Indicator 17**. Afforested land: Area supported for afforestation, **agroforestry** and restoration, including breakdowns (also included as one of the core set of indicators which must be reported on annually pursuant to Article 142)^[1]
- **Output Indicator 16**. Number of hectares or number of other units under maintenance commitments for afforestation and **agroforestry**

In addition to these mentions of “agroforestry”, Regulation 2021/2115 mentions “**shrubs and trees**” in two sections:

- **Article 4 Para 3 (c)**. - ‘permanent grassland and permanent pasture’ (together referred to as ‘permanent grassland’) shall be land that is used to grow grasses or other herbaceous forage naturally (self-seeded) or through cultivation (sown) and that has not been included in the crop rotation of the holding for five years or more and, where Member States so decide, that has not been ploughed up, or tilled, or reseeded with different types of grass or other herbaceous forage, for five years or more. **It may include other species, such as shrubs or trees, which can be grazed and, where Member States so decide, other species such as shrubs or trees which produce animal feed, provided that the grasses and other herbaceous forage remain predominant. Member States may also decide to consider the following types of land to be permanent grassland: (i) land which is covered by any of the species referred to in this point and which forms part of established local practices, where grasses and other herbaceous forage are traditionally not predominant**

² The Implementing Regulation ([L458 21.12.21](#)) further confirms that “information shall be provided on elements of agroforestry systems when it is established or maintained on the agricultural area, specifying these elements for each type of agricultural area (arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland)

or absent in grazing areas; (ii) land covered by any of the species referred to in this point, where grasses and other herbaceous forage are not predominant or are absent in grazing areas.

- **Result indicator 34.** Preserving landscape features: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees. This is also a core indicator for annual reporting.

The rules for “**conditionality**” (which all farmers must follow to receive basic payments) are defined in Annex 3 of Regulation 2021/2115, with nine “Good Agricultural and Environmental Practices” (GAEC) and 11 Statutory Management Requirements. Most of the GAECs can be contributed to by trees on agricultural land, but the rules for GAEC 8 (**minimum share of agricultural area devoted to non-productive areas or features**) – are particularly relevant since these “non-productive features” (Lawson, 2023) include productive trees and hedges[2]. There are three options available to farmers, depending on the choices made by Member States (MS) (but see section 3.6 for changes introduced in May 2024):

- Minimum share of at least 4% of arable land at farm level devoted to non-productive areas and features, including land lying fallow.
- Where a farmer commits to devote at least 7% of his/her arable land to non-productive areas or features, including land lying fallow, under an enhanced eco-scheme in accordance with Article 31(6), the share to be attributed to compliance with this GAEC standard shall be limited to 3%.
- Minimum share of at least 7% of arable land at farm level if this includes also catch crops or nitrogen fixing crops, cultivated without the use of plant protection products, of which 3% shall be land lying fallow or non-productive

2.2 CAP Horizontal Regulation (2021/2116)

This regulation on “**financing, management and monitoring** of the CAP” includes “agroforestry” in Article 25.1b to “Ensure agri-economic and agri-environmental-climate monitoring of agricultural land use and agricultural land use change, including agro-forestry...”.

This regulation is supplemented by **Commission Delegated Regulation 2021/2116**. Article 2 of this Regulation “**Identification System for Agricultural Parcels**” deals with ineligible elements (like trees) in section and Section 7 contains three subsections:

- A. ... to determine the maximum eligible area (for area based payments) MS shall **deduct ineligible elements** from the parcel by delineation, where possible, and define beforehand the criteria and procedures used to assess, quantify and where appropriate delineate the eligible and ineligible parts of the parcel... In defining the maximum eligible area, Member States **may set a reasonable margin** for correct quantification, to take account of the outline and condition of the parcel;
- B. ... to identify the agricultural area.. MS shall ensure the distinction of agricultural area in arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland, **including when they form agroforestry systems** on that area;
- C. ...as regards **permanent grassland with scattered ineligible features** MS may decided apply fixed reduction coefficients to determine the area considered eligible,³ and should register all relevant information.

This Delegated Regulation therefore appears to give multiple options to farmers with scattered trees in their parcels, depending on choices made by Member States, for example in the definition of Landscape Features:

³ as provided for in Article 4(4), point (b), third subparagraph of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115

- MS can allow isolated trees, lines of trees and groups of trees to be designated by farmers as Landscape Features – in which case the area they occupy is fully eligible for basic payments (See Section 3.1);
- MS can allow isolated fruit trees (and trees like cork oak or chestnut) to be designated as "permanent crops" – in which case the area they occupy is fully eligible for basic payment;
- MS could use subpara 7A above to delineate areas of ineligible trees which would be deducted from basic payments;
- MS could use subpara 7B above to delineate areas of "agroforestry" which would be fully eligible for basic payments, providing that the national definition of agroforestry is complied with;
- MS could use subpara 7C above – but only on permanent grassland – to calculate eligibility reduction coefficients – as has been the case in many MS in the CAP 2014-2022.

2.3 Delegated and Implementing Acts relating to the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation

These include:

- Implementing Regulation EU [2021/2289](#) on the content of CAP Strategic Plans and the electronic system for the secure exchange of information.
- Implementing Regulation EU [2021/2290](#) on the methods for the calculation of the common output and result indicators set out in Annex I of the SP Regulation.
- Implementing Regulation EU [2022/1475](#) on detailed rules for the evaluation of CAP Strategic Plans and provision of information for monitoring and evaluation

Implementing Regulation 2021/2289 is particularly important since it lays down the rules for GAEC 8 reporting, and clarifies that MS must give:

- An explanation of the choice of options made for the minimum share of arable land devoted to non productive areas and landscape features, particularly if not all three options land down in Annex III of Regulation 2021/2115 are applicable
- The specific share(s) of arable land subject to the standard
- An indication of landscape features and non-productive areas from the following indicative list: land lying fallow, hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, tree rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features, other
- For each type of Landscape Feature and non-productive area an indication should be given of the minimum size and weighting or conversion factors used for the calculation of the minimum share of landscape features and non-productive areas in arable land, according to their contribution to the biodiversity objective, where applicable;
- Information on the type of farmers concerned including exceptions
- List of landscape features concerned by the standard on the retention of landscape features
- Measures for avoiding invasive plant species where applicable

3 Policy Overview of 14 Member States

DigitAF members have participated in the CAP Network Task Group on CAP Implementation ([link](#)), and are engaged in working groups on CAP metrics, including Context, Impact and Result Indicators (see [fiches](#)), including the DG AGRI searchable database on Result Indicators ([here](#)) and the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework ([link](#)). Useful pan-European reviews of environmental aspects of the CAP include

- IEEP Environmental and climate assessment of strategic plans (France, Spain, Poland, Germany) Apr 23 ([link](#))
- CAP Unpacked - report by Birdlife, EEB and NABU - Dec 2022 ([link](#))
- ARC2020 - "Possible changes needed in CAP Strategic Plans to match - fit for 55" ([link](#))
- CAP Network "analytical work supporting the establishment of agroforestry systems ([26.9.2023](#))

3.1 Agroforestry Definitions

Member States were asked in the CAP Implementing Regulation to include minimum and maximum tree densities in their national definitions of agroforestry, and to specify specific conditions for arable land, grassland and permanent crop agroforestry. The thresholds specified are given in Table 1, with full details in EURAF [Policy Briefing #22](#)

Table 1 Summary of thresholds specified for agroforestry in the CAP Strategic Plans of 14 MS

	Country	Min trees /ha	Max trees/ha	Comment
1	BE-FL	30	300	higher densities for young trees
2	CZ	-	100	no different for young trees
3	DE	50	200	or in woody strips covering no more than 40% of area
4	DK	-	100	only fruit, berry or nut trees in AF, but other species in 20% "small habitats"
5	EL	5	250	scattered trees, trees in rows or on margins
6	ES	-	100	minimums are set by Regions
7	FI	-	50	number of trees does not include windbreaks in arable forestry
8	FR	-	-	trees can be isolated, in groups, or in rows
9	HU	-	250	also includes strops of short rotation coppice
10	IT	-	250	also includes linear systems
11	LV	-	100	also limit of total crown area of 500m2
12	NL	-	100	also specifies food forests and landscape elements
13	PT	40-60	-	focus on naturally regenerated trees excluding arable land
14	SL	-	50	or a canopy cover of less than 76%

Definitions which rely on numbers of trees per ha are difficult to monitor through remote sensing since few member states have defined what they mean by a "tree". Should only mature trees be counted, or do the thresholds apply to recently planted seedlings? The definitions of landscape-feature-trees are more precise, since these were stipulated for isolated trees or rows of trees in Article 45 of the original Greening Regulation (see [SWD\(2017\)121 final](#)) as having a crown-diameter of at least 4m. This minimum size tends still to be used by Member States in their definitions of landscape -features.

It is also clear from the specification of Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Result Indicator 17 (Table 2), that **woody landscape-features are considered as a component of agroforestry**. Sub indicator 17.3 is the total area of agroforestry, including planted woody landscape features and sub-indicator 17.4 is the area of the planted woody landscape features only. In reality, there will be two types of landscape feature: a) those which are declared by farmers in their IACS returns as official "landscape-features" and those which are not declared. The former will be fully eligible for basic payments (BISS) the latter reflects the fact that many farmers are not keen to have landscape features recognised since this constrains their management activities and their ability to remove these features.

Table 2: The subcategories to be reported under Result Indicator 17 ([Result Indicator Fiche, 12.7.22](#))

Unit of measurement	Hectares
Moment of data collection	Hectares covered by operations for which a first payment was made in the Financial Year concerned. This indicator is cumulative over the period
Methodology	For this indicator, four subcategories of area (hectares) of the first establishment and maintenance are included as soon as the beneficiary receives the first payment. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Afforested area 2. Restored area 3. Agro-forestry Remark: This sub-indicator measures the entire area supported under the intervention that is including the whole agroforestry system (both cultivated agricultural areas and areas under the planted landscape features) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Landscape features created Remark: This sub-indicator measures only area of planted wooded landscape features. To simplify measurement Member States may use conversion factors consistent with the design of the agroforestry intervention. These areas are accounted over the whole programming period.

3.2 Landscape Features (Pillar I)

There is confusion over whether landscape features are allowed in EU Legislation to be “productive” or not. The EU Biodiversity Strategy ([ref](#)) defines Landscape Features as including, “inter alia, buffer strips, rotational or non-rotational fallow land, hedges, **non-productive trees**, terrace walls, and ponds”. This wording is also used in the Nature Restoration Regulation ([ref](#)). Whereas the the Commission’s Implementing Regulation ([L/458/463](#)-Article 3.1 viii) for the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation ignores the “non-productive” adjective for trees and confirms that for GAEC8 Member States should select “**landscape features and non productive areas**” from the indicative list of “*land lying fallow, hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, trees rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features, other*”. The bizarre concept in the Biodiversity Strategy of “non-productive trees” is discussed in more detail [here](#).

EURAF produced [Policy Briefing #21](#) to summarise MS choices regarding Landscape Features. Woody landscape features are implemented by the majority of the 28 legislations: hedges or woody strips (20/28), trees in line (21/28), trees in groups/copses (24/28), isolated trees (19/28), forest edges (7/28). Further issues are (Table 4):

- All 28 legislations offer the 4% option for Landscape Features and fallow on arable land (although this is 10% for all agricultural land in the case of Ireland, and Finland permits only fallow land);
- 12 countries (AT, BEW, BG, DK, EE, EL, ES, HR, LT, LU, NL, PT) offer farmers an enhanced eco-scheme top up, in which case the GAEC 8 element on arable land is only 3%;
- 16 countries (BEF, BEW, BG, CY ,CS, EE, EL, ES, FR, HU, LT NL, PL, PT, RO, SK) offer the old "greening" option of Landscape Features and fallow plus N-fixing crops and catch crops - adding to a total of 7% arable land;
- 8 countries appear to offer farmers all three choices (BEW, BG, EE, EL, ES, LT ,NL, PT).

There are however significant gaps in the details provided on the permitted dimensions of Tree Landscape Features :

- Around half legislations have some missing multiplication or weighting factors
- Of the 20 legislations which recognise hedges, 5 do not give details of permitted width, length and gaps
- Of the 21 legislations which recognise trees in line, 7 do not give details of crown size or permitted gaps.
- Of the 19 legislations which recognise isolated trees, 11 do not give details of permitted crown size
- A majority of legislations specify a maximum block size for “trees in groups/copses” which is either smaller or larger than the block size defined in their national legislation for “forest land”. These differences will complicate the administration of national IACS/LPIS systems and GHG reporting

The above selection by legislations of tree-landscape-features has significantly increased from the previous CAP, when only 17 recognised Hedges or woody strips, 13 isolated trees, 16 trees in line, and 18 trees in groups (Table 5).

3.3 Permanent Grassland Definitions (Pillar I)

The CAP "Omnibus Regulation" in December 2017 ([ref](#)) widened and clarified a number of definitions including that for "Permanent Grassland". Choices were however left in the hands of Member States. The CAP Strategic Plan Regulation widened ever further the choice available in the definition of "permanent grassland", including not only trees and shrubs when grasses "remain predominant", but also the option to include trees and shrubs, **even when no grasses are present**. Only three countries (IE, EL, ES) have implemented this latter option over their whole territories, but seven legislations (BEW, CY, DE, FR, IT, PT, SE) have implemented it in at least part of their area. A further three countries (BG ,FI, RO) allow shrubs

and trees to be part of permanent grassland as long as grasses remain predominant (Table 6). These choices are important for farmers since they determine eligibility for CAP Basic Payments (BISS). Issues are discussed further in EURAF [Policy Briefing #29](#).

While there are clear statistics for a reduction in animal numbers in the EU since 1990 (Figure 1), there is little evidence of any reduction in the area of permanent pasture as recorded by farmers in their returns to EU Farm Structure Surveys (Table 3). Thus EU pastoralism is becoming more extensive, without evidence of abandonment of permanent grasslands on a European scale, although the situation in some European countries may be different (Rubio Delgado *et al.*, 2023).

Table 3: Areas of farmland (ha) including arable land, permanent grassland and permanent crops in the EU-27 Farm Structure Survey (FSS). Showing % “change” between 2005 and 2020 - full data by country [here](#).

	Farm area	UAA	Arable land	Perm grassland	Perm crops	Kitchen gardens	Unutilised agric	Wooded areas	Other areas on
2005	198,906,760	156,039,240	98,602,690	46,174,950	10,835,810	425,810	3,332,490	30,712,890	8,821,230
2007	199,537,110	157,333,230	99,068,370	46,889,610	10,982,370	392,890	2,994,680	30,460,600	8,747,700
2010	199,225,780	158,963,800	97,977,120	49,940,310	10,666,430	349,580	3,543,960	29,498,350	7,218,120
2013	195,045,590	157,254,840	97,933,440	48,769,070	10,266,850	285,770	2,533,580	28,358,480	6,897,400
2016	191,888,000	156,658,530	97,078,750	48,865,000	10,467,560	247,160	1,707,740	26,931,300	6,589,360
2020	190,382,400	157,415,700	98,094,800	47,963,700	11,138,530	205,020	2,040,320	24,092,370	6,832,800
Change%	-4.29%	0.88%	-0.52%	3.87%	2.79%	-51.85%	-38.77%	-21.56%	-22.54%

Figure 1: Decline in livestock numbers in the EU between 2000 and 2020, with 2010 as 1 (when there were 152.5 million [pigs](#), 83.8 million [cattle](#), 74.8 million [sheep](#) and 13.2 million [goats](#) (Eurostat 2023)).

Table 4. Elements of Landscape Features and Non-Productive Areas (including numbers of sub-elements) selected in the CAP Strategic Plans of Member States (CAP 2023-2028). For details see [this spreadsheet](#).⁴

CAP-M	Landscape feature and non productive area	AT	BEF	BEW	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HU	HR	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SK	SI	Sum		
B151	Fallow Land	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1			2		2	1	2		3			30		
B152	Hedges or woody strips	1	1	1	1			1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1		1	1		1	1	20		
B152	Trees in Line		1	1	1		1	1		1	1	1		1		1	1	1			1	1		1	2	1	1		1	1	21	
B152	Trees in Groups/ Copses	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1		1	2	1	1		1	1	24		
B152	Isolated Trees			1	1	1	1	1			1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1		1		1	1		1	1	19		
B153	Buffer Strips	1	1	1	1				1								1	1			1	1	1				1		1	1	13	
B153	Field Margins (# types)		1	3	1	2	7	1	1	1		1		1	2		7	1	1	4	1		4		1	1	2	1		44		
B153	Forest Edge Strips - non prod		1	1	1					1		1				1	1													7		
B154	Ditches			1			1			1	1			1		1	1	1	1		1		3	1	1	1				16		
B154	Streams										1											1	1							3		
B155	Small Ponds	1	1	1							1	1		1	1		1	1	1	1		1	1		1				1	15		
B155	Small Wetlands					1	1				1										1	1	1	1	1					8		
B156	Traditional Stone Walls	1					1		1	1	1	1		1		1	1	1			1	1							1	12		
B157	Cairns	1					1				1	1							1	1	1					1				8		
B158	Terraces					1	1				1	1			1			1					1						y	7		
B159	Cultural Features	1		5				1	1	1	1	1			1		1							1						13		
B160	Others			1			2	1	1			2						1	1					4	1	1			-	15		
B161	Cover or catch crops (7% option)		-	-		1		-	-	-	-			1	1					-			-		-					3		
B162	N-Fixing Crops (7% option)		-	-		1			1	-	-			1	1					-			-		-				-	4		
	Total elements / sub-elements active	8	8	19	8	4	18	11	6	11	13	14	1	11	12	8	16	12	8	11	11	6	21	9	10	8	5	6	7	282		
	4% Option	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	28		
	3% Option	y		y	y			y	y	y	y	y				y			y	y				y		y				12		
	7% Option		y	y	y	y	y			y	y	y		y	y				y					y	y	y	y		y	16		
	LULUCF Regulation - threshold of "forest land" (ha)	0.05	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.05	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.5	0.1	1	0.25	0.5	0.3	0.25			
	Strategic Plan - max LF copse/grove size (ha)	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	?	0.2	?	?	?	0.3	-	0.5	0.5	?	-	0.3		0.3	0.5	-	1.5	0.5	0.5	0.9	-	?	0.5			
	Details of hedge width and permitted gaps?	y	y	y	y			y		y		y		y	y	y			y	y	y			y			y			15		
	Details of permitted crown size of trees in line?		y	y	y					y				y			y			y		y		y	y	y	y		y	13		
	Details of crown size of isolated trees?			y	y										y	y				y				y	y				y	8		
	RED shows where the definition of "copse/grove" on agricultural land differs from the national definition the minimum size threshold for a forest block. In many countries the size threshold is not given or copses/groves are not recognised as Landscape Features																															

⁴ CAP-M = CAP Monitoring Database codes (data is confidential to Member States). It is surprising that the same code will be used for all woody features.

Table 5 Landscape Features and Ecological Focus Areas selected by Member States as part of Greening Measures in the CAP 2014-22 (Lawson et al., 2016)

CAP-M	Country	AT	BEF	BEW	BG	CY	CZ	DK	DE	EE	IE	EL	ES	FR	HR	IT	LV	LT	LU	HU	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SI	SK	FI	SE	UKE	UKN	UKS	UKW	Sum		
B151	Fallow Land	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	30	
B152	Hedges or woody strips		A	G	A				G	G	G			A	G	GS			S	A			A		A					G	G			A	16	
B152	Trees in Line			G	A		G		G	G	G	AG		A	G	GS			S	A	A		A		A		GS								16	
B152	Trees in Groups/ Copses		A	G	A		G		G	G	A	AG		A	G	A	A		S	G	A		A		A		GS								18	
B152	Isolated Trees			G	A		G		G					A	G	GS			S	AG	A		AG		A		GS								13	
B153	Buffer Strips		Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y		Y	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y			Y		Y		Y		Y			Y		Y	19	
B153	Field Margins		A	G	AG		A		AG					A		A	A		A	A	A	A	A		A		GS		A			A			17	
B153	Forest Edge Strips - non prod		Y	Y	Y	Y			Y					Y	Y	Y			Y	Y			Y												11	
B154	Ditches	G	A	G	A		G	G	G	G	G	A		A	G	GS				A			AG		A						G				17	
B154	Streams																																		0	
B155	Ponds	G	A	G	A									A	G	GS	A		S	G			AG		A										12	
B155	Small wetlands																																		0	
B156	Traditional Stone Walls	G							G	G				A	G	GS															G		A		8	
B158	Terraces				Y		Y		Y					Y		Y				Y						Y		Y							8	
B160	Other Landscape Features	G				Y	G	G			G					Y	G			G	G			GS				G			G				12	
B161	Cover or catch crops	Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y	Y		Y			Y	Y		Y		Y	Y		Y	Y		Y	Y	Y		Y	Y		Y		Y	21	
B162	N-Fixing Crops	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	31
	x - Afforested areas		Y			Y	Y		Y		Y		Y	Y		Y			Y	Y			Y	Y	Y						Y		Y		15	
	x - Forest Edge Strips - productive		Y				Y							Y		Y			Y	Y			Y												7	
	x - Hectares of Agroforestry (ha)		YY	Y		Y			Y				YY	YY		YY			Y	YY				YY							YY				11	
	x - Short rotation coppice	Y	Y	Y	Y		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y			Y	Y	Y			Y	Y		Y	Y		Y		Y	Y	Y		Y		Y		22	
	Total EFA Elements Active	8	14	14	14	6	13	6	17	8	11	6	4	18	13	18	8	2	15	18	7	4	15	5	13	3	10	4	5	5	9	5	6			
	G=GAEC7, S = Statutory Requirements 2 and or 3; A = Article 45 of the EFA regulation																																			
	YY= Activated as EFA in Pillar I AND Agroforestry used as rural development measure in Pillar II																																			

Table 6 Permanent Grassland definitions implemented by Member States. For details see [this spreadsheet](#). Ten countries implement the option to include up to 100% trees and shrubs in their Permanent Grassland definition on at least part of their territories.

Use of optional parts of Permanent Grassland Definition	AT	BE-F	BE-W	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HU	HR	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SK	SL
4.1.2.4.1 Definition of grasses and other herbaceous forage																												
4.1.2.4.2 Decision to use 'ploughing' criterion in relation to permanent grassland classification	n	n	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	y	y	n	y	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	n
4.1.2.4.3 Decision to use 'tilling' criterion in relation to permanent grassland classification	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	y	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n
4.1.2.4.4 Decision to use 'reseeding with different types of grasses' criterion in relation to permanent grassland classification and its description in case of affirmative reply	y	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	y	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n
4.1.2.4.5 Decision regarding the inclusion of other species such as trees and/or shrubs which produce animal feed, provided that grasses and other herbaceous forage remain predominant	n	n	n	y	n	n	y	n	n	y	y	y	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	n
4.1.2.4.6 Decision regarding the inclusion of other species, such as shrubs and/or trees, which could be grazed and/or which produce animal feed, where grasses and other herbaceous forage are traditionally not predominant or are absent in grazing areas	n	n	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	y	y	n	y	n	n	y	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n
a) if affirmative is this applicable to all regions	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	y	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n
b) if not all regions is it only applicable to "established local practices"	n	n	y	n	y	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	y	n	n
c) if not all regions is it applicable to areas other than "established local practices"	n	n	-	-	y	n	-	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	n	n	-	n	n	n	n	n	n	-	n	n	n	n

3.4 Eco-schemes (Pillar I - Article 31)

Only two agroforestry or landscape-feature eco-schemes have been implemented in the 14 DigitAF countries - Germany and Greece (Table 7), and these have rather small payments specifically focused on existing areas of trees and small woodlands. In the case of Germany these payments are limited to the areas under the trees (Table 7). In 10 of the 14 countries there are other eco-schemes which "could" be appropriate for agroforestry and landscape-features, but only if the existing rules are clarified. This clarification may be facilitated by the new "CAP Simplification Regulation" (Section 3.6).

Table 6 Eco-schemes (CAP Article 31) which mention agroforestry (code 1) or landscape features (code 2).

AF/LF	MS	Article	Code	O.16 (tc)	R.17 (total)	Measure
1	DE	Art 31	DZ-0403 –			Maintaining agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland
1 2	EL	Art 31	P1-31.05 –		€66,564,568	Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems, rich in landscape elements
2	EL	Art 31	P1-31.10 –			Protection of landscapes and environmentally significant agricultural systems agricultural systems
2	IT	Art 31	ES 3			Safeguarding of olive trees of particular landscape value
2	LT	Art 31	Tl05eko1.5			Maintenance of Landscape Elements

3.5 Rural Development (Pillar II)

Schemes which potentially include agroforestry could be found in four CAP Strategic Plan Sections (ENVCLIM, INVEST, COOP, KNOW) related to 5 Articles in the Strategic Plan Regulation (2021/2115).

- Article 70 ENVCLIM- Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments
- Article 73 INVEST Investments in tangible and intangible assets which contribute to CAP objectives
- Article 74 INVEST - Investments in irrigation
- Article 77 COOP - Cooperation - including EIP operational groups and LEADER
- Article 78 KNOW Knowledge exchange and dissemination of information.

Investment (INVEST) measures pay site preparation and establishment costs for a single year only. They are provided only in 6 administrations (CZ, ES, IT, PL, PT, SK). The figure shown for R.17 is the total expenditure on tree planting (afforestation, restoration, agroforestry, landscape features) for all CAP measures in a given country, no specific breakdown is usually provided for the spend on afforestation (sub indicator 17.3)

Table 7 Investment measures available for establishing agroforestry in the 2023-2027 CAP

AF/LF	MS	Article	Code	O.16 (tc)	R.17 (total)	Measure
1	CZ	Art 73-74	42.73		€3,917,700	Establishment of an agroforestry system
1	ES	Art 73-74	6881.1		€68,809,809	Non productive investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems
1	IT	Art 73/74	SRD05		€47,387,981	Forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems on agricultural land
1	PL	Art 73-74	I 10.13.		€5,998,785	Establishment of agroforestry systems
1	PT	Art 73-74	C.3.2.2		€3,360,000	Setting up agroforestry systems
1	PT	Art 73-74	F.2.2		€300,000	Investment in the creation and regeneration of agroforestry systems
1	SK	Art 73-74	73.01		€2,932,150	Establishing an agroforestry system

There are almost 60 investment measures which may support agroforestry or landscape features (Table 8), but which do not mention support for tree planting (R.17), or if they do which appear to be limited to conventional afforestation.

There are 11 Agri-environment Climate Measures in 11 countries which support annual payments for agroforestry or landscape features (Table 8) and around 100 measures which *may support this*, but which made no specific mention of trees.

Table 8 AECM Measures (Article 70) which support activities related to environment and climate and which mention agroforestry or landscape features

AF/IF	MS	Article	Code	R.17 (to)	Measure
2	BE-FL	Art 70	3.9		Management agreements for the maintenance of woody small landscape elements
1	CZ	Art 70	26.7		Caring for an established agroforestry system
2	EL	Art 70	P3-70-1.2		Support for the protection of the rural landscape
2	FI	Art 70	Environment 10		Management of agricultural nature and landscape
2	FR	Art 70	70.22		Agri-environmental and climate commitments: "Restoration of the landscape mosaic and fire prevention" - Corsica
2	HR	Art 70	70.7		Preservation of landscape features
2	IT	Art 70	SRA25 ACA25		Protection of tree crops with environmental and landscape value
2	NL	Art 70	I.70.1		Agricultural nature and landscape management (ANLb)
1	PL	Art 70	I.8.8		Afforestation and afforestation premiums and agroforestry schemes
2	PT	Art 70	C.1.1.2.2		Permanent Crops and Traditional Landscapes
2	SL	Art 70	IRP 18.03		Biodiversity and landscape

Table 9 Investments measures (Article 73/74) in Member States which may be relevant for the agroforestry but where no specific mention of agroforestry is made. Some measures are mapped to Result Indicator 17 and involve tree planting, but in all circumstances this appears to be limited to conventional afforestation.

MS	Article	Code	R.17 (total)	Measure
AT	Art 73-74	73-13		Implementation of climate and energy projects at local level
BE-FL	Art 73-74	3.21		Innovative green investments on farms
BE-FL	Art 73-74	3.22		Productive investments for further sustainability on farms
BE-FL	Art 73-74	3.23		Productive green investments on farms
BE-FL	Art 73-74	3.24		Productive investments for animal welfare on farms
BE-FL	Art 73-74	3.26	€15,213,000	Non-productive investments for environmental and climate goals
BE-W	Art 73-74	355		Aid for non-productive investments in rural areas & restoration of ecosystem services
BG	Art 73-74	II.D.4		Restoring agricultural potential after natural disasters or catastrophic events and investment in appropriate preventive actions
BG	Art 73-74	II.D.8	€5,000,000	Non-productive investments in agricultural holdings
BG	Art 73-74	II.D.10	€2,932,150	Afforestation and restoration
BG	Art 73-74	II.D.13		Reducing biodiversity loss, conserving forests habitats and reduce illegal activities in forest areas
CY	Art 73-74	AA4.3.4	€650,000	Afforestation and woodland creation
CZ	Art 73-74	44.73		Conversion of replacement tree stands
CZ	Art 73-74	46.73		Landscaping
DE	Art 73-74	EL-0404		Investments in agricultural and forestry infrastructure, including rural land readjustment
DE	Art 73-74	EL-0407		Non productive investments in the forest sector
DE	Art 73-74	EL-0411		Support for diversification of agricultural holdings
DK	Art 73-74	18		Water and climate projects
DK	Art 73-74	20	€35,392,912	Private afforestation
EE	Art 73-74	KK2.2		Investing in forests to adapt to climate change (non-productive investments)
EE	Art 73-74	KK3		Land-based environmental protection structures
EL	Art 73-74	P3-73-1.1		Land improvement infrastructure projects
EL	Art 73-74	P3-73-1.3	€60,364,707	Prevention and restoration of damage to forests due to fires, natural disasters and conservation of forest genetic resources
EL	Art 73-74	P3-73-1.4		Unconditional infrastructure projects for land improvements aimed at improving the competitiveness
EL	Art 73-74	P3-73-3.3		Non-productive investments for protection against erosion, for containment soil water and nutrients, through new terraces
EL	Art 73-74	P3-73-3.4	€27,450,899	Non-productive investments for the establishment of forest plantations (phase a) afforestation of agricultural land)
ES	Art 73-74	6841.2		Aid and investments to modernise agriculture
ES	Art 73-74	6871		Non productive investments on environmental services
ES	Art 73-74	6881.2		Non productive investments in forest fire protection
ES	Art 73-74	6881.4		Non productive investments in forest management for environmental objectives
HR	Art 73-74	73.01	€20,400,000	Non-productive investments in agriculture for nature and the environment
HR	Art 73-74	73.05	€11,764,706	Reconstruction (conversion) of degraded forests
LT	Art 73-74	KP02mva	€7,000,000	Reforestation and restoration
LT	Art 73-74	KP08neg1		Non-productive investments related to biodiversity, habitats, landscapes restoration and conservation
LT	Art 73-74	KP31tvi		Sustainable investments in agricultural holdings
MT	Art 73-74	Off Farm NP INVST	€1,250,000	Off-farm Non-Productive Investments and Afforestation
MT	Art 73-74	Off-Farm P.INVEST	€8,750,000	Off-farm Productive Investment
NL	Art 73-75	I.73.1b	€50,640,000	Productive investments Green - Blue and animal welfare.
PL	Art 73-74	I.10.11.	€11,620,525	Afforestation of agricultural land
PL	Art 73-74	I.10.12.	€6,003,105	Creation of mid-field woodlots.
PL	Art 73-74	I.10.14	€11,999,935	Enhancing the biodiversity of private forests
PL	Art 73-74	I.10.4		Investments contributing to environmental and climate protection
PT	Art 73-74	C.3.2.5	€64,000,000	Promoting ecosystem services
PT	Art 73-74	C.4.1.2		Prevention of natural calamities
PT	Art 73-74	E.6.1		Preventive actions
PT	Art 73-74	E.8.2	€170,000	Improving the Resilience and Environmental Value of Forest Ecosystems (non-productive)
PT	Art 73-74	F.1.7		Non-productive Investments
PT	Art 73-74	F.2.1	€2,500,000	Investment in afforestation and tree planting
RO	Art 73-74	DR-19	€11,764,706	Unproductive investments at farm level
RO	Art 73-74	DR-29		Investment in the creation and development of non-agricultural activities
SL	Art 73-74	IRP22		Non-productive investments linked to the implementation of nature conservation sub-interventions
SL	Art 73-74	IRP23		Habitat types and species in Natura 2000 areas
SK	Art 73-74	73.02	€196,986	Establishment of linear vegetation elements
SK	Art 73-74	73.03	€685,632	Afforestation of agricultural land
SK	Art 73-74	73.16	€20,000,000	Forest restoration projects
SK	Art 73-74	73.18	€40,000,000	Construction of common facilities and measures - green and blue infrastructure elements
SK	Art 73-74	73.21		Improvement of forest management practices in forests up to 500ha (unproductive investments)

Funding for agroforestry in Cooperation (COOP) and Knowledge Exchange (KNOW) are only mentioned in the French CAP Strategic Plan.

3.6 The EU “CAP Simplification Regulation”

A recent policy change is that the "CAP Simplification" Regulation, adopted in May 2024 ([link](#)), has removed the obligation for farmers to meet the 4% threshold for GAEC8 on arable land (Landscape Features and Non-productive Areas), but replaced this with a requirement that all legislations should introduce an eco-scheme "to support to farmers for keeping a share of arable land in non-productive state or to create new landscape features".

Woody landscape features are an important part of GAEC8, and the change to a "carrot rather than stick" approach to landscape features could be very important, particularly since it can (potentially) apply to both croplands and grasslands and is the first eco-scheme which is "mandatory" for member states. Transitional arrangements mean that those countries which already have an eco-scheme supporting landscape features can implement the exemption from GAEC8 in 2024, otherwise they should introduce such a scheme and gain GAEC-8 exemption in 2025.

3.7 The Nature Restoration Regulation

The Nature Restoration Regulation gained parliamentary approval on 27/2/24 and was eventually approved by Council on 17/6/24. The approved text ([ref](#)) removed the initial mention of retaining 10% "high diversity landscape features" and does not mention the 4% target. It does however say in Article 11 ("restoration of agricultural ecosystems" that:

*Member States shall put in place measures which shall aim to achieve an increasing trend at national level of at least two out of the three following indicators for agricultural ecosystems, as further specified in Annex IV, measured in the period from ... [the date of entry into force of this Regulation] until 31 December 2030, and every six years thereafter, until the satisfactory levels as set in accordance with Article 14(5) are reached: (a) grassland butterfly index; (b) stock of organic carbon in cropland mineral soils; (c) **share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features.***

Additionally, In Article 14 ("preparation of national restoration plans") para 7, it is confirmed that:

*Each Member State may, by ... [one year from the date of entry into force of this Regulation], develop a methodology to complement the methodology referred to in Annex IV⁵, in order to monitor high-diversity landscape features not covered by the common method referred to in the description of high-diversity landscape features in that Annex. **The Commission shall provide guidance on the framework for developing such methodologies by [one month from the date of entry into force of this Regulation].***

It is the intention of DigitAF WP1 to provide a comparison of the ways in which Member States are using LPIS-based monitoring systems to: a) track progress towards national landscape-feature targets, b) compare national data with the Pan-European methodologies of JRC and EEA, and c) assist creation of national frameworks in some MS where landscape-features can be identified on a farm-by-farm basis and potentially used for future "payment by results" - with recognition for past efforts, at least back to 2005⁶

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/lan_esms.htm

⁶ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC102591>

3.8 The LULUCF Regulation and National Energy and Climate Plans

The revised LULUCF Regulation 2023 ([ref](#)) sets a target for member states collectively to meet net removals target of 310 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent by the year 2030. This is allocated amongst member states according to the share shown in Table 10

Table 10 The Union target (column D), the average greenhouse gas inventory data for the years 2016-2018 (column B) and national targets for Member States in 2030 (column C). LULUCF Regulation 2023/839

A	B	C	D
Member State	The average greenhouse gas inventory data for the years 2016, 2017 and 2018 (kt of CO ₂ equivalent), 2020 submission	Member State targets, 2030 (kt of CO ₂ equivalent)	Value of the greenhouse gas net removals (kt of CO ₂ equivalent) in 2030, 2020 submission (Columns B+C)
Belgium	- 1 032	- 320	- 1 352
Bulgaria	- 8 554	- 1 163	- 9 718
Czech Republic	- 401	- 827	- 1 228
Denmark	5 779	- 441	5 338
Germany	- 27 089	- 3 751	- 30 840
Estonia	- 2 112	- 434	- 2 545
Ireland	4 354	- 626	3 728
Greece	- 3 219	- 1 154	- 4 373
Spain	- 38 326	- 5 309	- 43 635
France	- 27 353	- 6 693	- 34 046
Croatia	- 4 933	- 593	- 5 527
Italy	- 32 599	- 3 158	- 35 758
Cyprus	- 289	- 63	- 352
Latvia	- 6	- 639	- 644
Lithuania	- 3 972	- 661	- 4 633
Luxembourg	- 376	- 27	- 403
Hungary	- 4 791	- 934	- 5 724
Malta	4	- 2	2
Netherlands	4 958	- 435	4 523
Austria	- 4 771	- 879	- 5 650
Poland	- 34 820	- 3 278	- 38 098
Portugal	- 390	- 968	- 1 358
Romania	- 23 285	- 2 380	- 25 665
Slovenia	67	- 212	- 146
Slovakia	- 6 317	- 504	- 6 821
Finland	- 14 865	- 2 889	- 17 754
Sweden	- 43 366	- 3 955	- 47 321
EU-27/Union	- 267 704	- 42 296	- 310 000*

Member States were expected to amend their National Energy and Climate Plans by June 2023 to provide a roadmap from 2025 onwards of how these 2030 targets will be achieved. Few countries have done this however. In the words of a EU-wide assessment of the draft updated NECP by DG CLIMA on December 2023 ([ref](#)):

*The majority of the draft updated NECPs do not show sufficient ambition and action on emissions from the land sector. Very few Member States show a concrete pathway to reach their national net removal targets, or sufficient actions to assist farmers, foresters and other stakeholders in building sustainable business models in line with these targets. The aggregation of the LULUCF projections shows that the overall net removals would still lead to a gap of around -40 to -50 Mt CO₂ eq. compared to the 2030 target of -310 Mt CO₂ eq¹⁵ **Almost all Member States need to improve their monitoring, reporting and verification to ensure the robustness and policy integration enhancements of the revised legislation.** Finally, biodiversity, nature restoration and nature-based solutions should be better integrated in the plans, to enhance carbon sinks and resilience. The effective implementation of the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products will also contribute to counter this trend.*

It is clear that EU forests alone will not be sufficient to meet the 2030 targets, let alone the land sector neutrality envisaged in the EU for 2040 (. The potential contribution of agroforestry is considered in EURAF

[Policy Briefing #26](#), and the climate-adaptation benefits of agroforestry in [Policy Briefing #27](#). The potential role of agroforestry in meeting 2040 climate targets is considered in EURAF's Press Release of [6.2.24](#) and in the Brno Agroforestry Declaration of [2.6.24](#).

DigitAF WP1 is due in M36 to complete a deliverable titled “*Evaluation and recommendations on methods used by MS to record AF areas and GHG emissions*” This will consider the extent to which Member States are recording trees on grassland and cropland: including the identification of polygons containing trees and the methods used to calculate their emissions. Plans developed in the NECPs of all Member States will feed into this deliverable and recommendations will be made to Member States for greater inclusion of the potential of trees outside forests to contribute to the targets. This study will provide a link to the quantification at a national scale of the impact of agroforestry-carbon-farming discussed in the next section.

3.9 Agroforestry in the EU Framework Regulation for Carbon Removals (CRCF)

As part of an update of EURAF [Policy Briefing #8](#) on Carbon Farming (Kay, Lawson and Bertomeu, 2023) we reviewed the literature on sequestration of agroforestry systems in temperate regions and used 2018 Copernicus data on tree crown density superimposed on Corine estimates of agricultural land cover, to evaluate the scope for very-large scale afforestation and agroforestation. This focused on those areas in Member States which have fewest trees, which are usually the areas of greatest environmental pressure (Kay *et al.*, 2019), with mineral soils which will benefit most from the introduction of small forest-blocks, agroforestry and landscape features.

Around 27 studies reported reliably on temperate agroforestry sequestration data (6 Atlantic, 7 Continental, 12 Mediterranean, 4 Canada/USA). Some of them recorded whole system biomass and carbon stocks, others evaluated the annual prunings and residues. Several combined measured and modelled data, to account for the whole lifespan of an agroforestry system – from planting to harvesting. The average agroforestry system captured around 1.44 t C/ha/yr or 5.27 t CO₂/ha/yr aboveground. Systems ranged from 0.15-0.90 t C/ha/year in Mediterranean oak in Dehesa or Montado systems to 5 t C/ha/year in dense poplar agroforestry systems in the UK.

Excluding Natura 2000 areas, we concluded that more than 77% of EU agricultural land (~130 Mha) has less than 10% tree crown cover and almost 60% has zero tree cover (~100 Mha). Therefore, there seems to be an excellent opportunity to increase tree-cover on all agricultural land to 10%, by introducing an emergency programme of small-scale afforestation and agroforestation (Figure 1). The latter has the advantage of keeping land in "official" agricultural use and retaining eligibility for agricultural basic payments. If an average total (above- and below-ground) sequestration of 5 tCO₂e/ha/yr is assumed for the EU, an emergency tree-planting programme of 1 million hectares per year, starting in 2025, would generate around 80 Mt CO₂e/yr by 2040. This will go a long way to filling the estimated annual net-emissions gap in the land sector (AFOLU)⁷ in 2040 of 110-120 Mt CO₂e. It assumes, however, a scale of tree-planting completely without precedent in Member States. The currently proposed planting area in CAP Strategic Plans over the seven-year period from 2023-2029 is only 0.619 million hectares.

We recommend that Member States combine the CAP Payments discussed above and fully integrate CAP funding with eventual "adoption" of agroforestry areas into agroforestry-carbon-farming-schemes. This would allow CAP Ecoschemes (Article 31) to support planning for tree-planting and baseline soil sampling (year 0), CAP Investment Measures (Article 73/74) to support tree-planting (year 1), CAP Agri-Environment Climate Measures (Article 70) to support annual payments (years 2-7). Followed by payments from carbon certification through the remainder of the agroforestry rotation, supported by an agroforestry management plan which describes the monitoring needed for GHG MRV, and the criteria needed to demonstrate sustainability following the criteria set in the EU Sustainable Finance Initiative (aka the Taxonomy Regulation) - see EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#).

⁷ This assumes that non-CO₂ emissions from EU Agriculture will remain approximately static at 380 MtCO₂e/yr

Figure 1. Tree-Cover-Density in agricultural land in the 39 EEA countries. The red areas are priority planting areas where this index is particularly low. Source: COPERNICUS Tree-Cover-Density (TCD) for 2018 superimposed on CORINE agricultural land for 2018. Each pixel covers 1ha (100x100m). EURAF's goal is to assist Member States and civil society turn this map green by 2040 to help meet the net-zero emissions challenge.

3.10 Conclusions and future work.

This report primarily reports on agroforestry-related policies in the CAP Strategic Plans of EU Member States, and provides links to national Briefings where developments in these policies are being tracked. These Briefings will be made available to the EURAF Community on zenodo.org.

It is disappointing that there are currently only 17 measures from 9 countries which specifically mention agroforestry. This is 17 from a total of 950 ecoschemes, investment measures and agri-environment-climate measures. However, recent confirmation that agroforestry will be "one of the first, if not the first" types of carbon farming certified through the EU Carbon Removals Certification Framework (see [EURAF Press Release](#)), gives us confidence in the increasing role which agroforestry will play in EU climate, environmental and agricultural policies. The following actions were suggested in a recent [presentation](#) on carbon-farming policies at the 7th European Agroforestry Conference.

1. MS should share spatial databases used in national LULUCF calculations at parcel scale
2. MS should integrate forestry and agricultural parcels in Open Source Rural Cadastres.
3. MS should include calculations of the impact of their current CAP policies on GHG emissions and include in their National Energy and Climate Plans
4. MS should include all the tree-based landscape feature options in CAP Plans
5. MS should support carbon farming sequentially (Pillar 1 > Pillar II > voluntary carbon farming > Agri-ETS?)

6. MS and Regions should sign up to the EURAF target of 10% tree-crown-cover on all grassland and cropland by 2040
7. EU Commission should move forward rapidly with GreenData4All and FaST Platform data
8. Farmers should be incentivised to use the landscape features option in their Geospatial Aid Applications
9. Farmers and landowners should develop agroforestry tenancy agreements
10. Foresters should work with farmers/shepherds for fire abatement planning and animal welfare in and around forests.
11. Projects should cooperate on geospatial living labs LTMS and metadata standards (e.g. Bonares)
12. Projects should interact with MS in LULUCF, CRCF, Effort Sharing and NECPs

A second [presentation](#) at the 7th European Agroforestry Conference covers the content of this report.

This report is DigitAF Deliverable 1.1. Further planned deliverables in Workpackage 1 are

- 1.2 “Report on availability of agri-environment indexes in MS at NUTS3 level and options for data collection at farm scale” (Agroscope, M30)
- 1.3 “Evaluation and recommendations on methods used by MS to record AF areas and GHG emissions” (EFI M36)
- 1.4 “Policies and MRV models for carbon farming in the voluntary and statutory sectors” (ELO, draft M40, update M48)
- 1.5 "Agroforestry models implemented using LPIS spatial data for use in DigitAF Living Labs" (MVARC , M36)
- 1.6: Evaluation of implementation of national CAP Strategic Plan measures for the establishment and maintenance of agroforestry and landscape features. (EURAF, M48)

ANNEXES

A Belgium - Flanders

The section on Flanders has been replaced by a DRAFT of [EURAF Policy Briefing #31](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Flemish.

B Czechia

The section on Czechia has been replaced by a DRAFT of [EURAF Policy Briefing #32](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Czech.

C Denmark

The section on Denmark has been replaced by a DRAFT of [EURAF Policy Briefing #33](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Danish.

D Finland

The section on Finland has been replaced by a DRAFT of [EURAF Policy Briefing #34](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Finish

E France

The section on France has been replaced by a DRAFT of [EURAF Policy Briefing #35](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and French

F Germany

The section on Germany has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #36](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and German.

G Greece

The section on Greece has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #37](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Greek.

H Hungary

The section on Hungary has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #38](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Hungarian.

I Italy

The section on Italy has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #39](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Italian.

J Latvia

The section on Latvia has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #40](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Latvian.

K Netherlands

The section on Latvia has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #41](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Dutch.

L Portugal

The section on Portugal (continental) has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #42](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Portuguese.

M Slovenia

The section on Slovenia has been replaced by a Draft of [EURAF Policy Briefing #43](#). This will be completed by September 2024 and published on Zenodo.org in both English and Slovenian.

N Spain

This section has been replaced by [EURAF Policy Briefing #44](#). It is available on zenodo.org in [English](#) and [Spanish](#).

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